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Laboratory learning: Influence of the perceived laboratory mode on learning outcomes

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of the second phase of a study that investigated differences in learning outcomes of university students who conducted laboratory experiments in two different modes in the local domain: hands-on and simulated. In order to keep constant as many variables as possible (such as experimental approach, learning objectives and tests, supervision, teaching materials), a crossover study approach was deployed. During the first phase of the study, it was found that there were statistically significant differences in learning outcomes of 102 study participants, favouring the hands-on mode. Since laboratory experiments in both modes were created to be very similar, the reason for this difference needed clarification. It was hypothesised that the difference in learning outcomes originated from different perceptions on the efficacy of hands-on and simulated experiments. In order to check this hypothesis, a modified second phase of the study with 113 subjects was conducted. This time, in order to ensure that the mode of a laboratory experiment will not be an influencing factor, all participants used hands-on equipment for laboratory experiments. Subjects from one group actually used hands-on equipment. Subject from the other group only thought that they are conducting hands-on experiments. In fact, their equipment was 'modified' to display the results of simulated experiments. The outcomes of the second phase of the study supported the 'perception' hypothesis. No statistically significant differences in learning outcomes of the subjects from the second phase of the experiment were discovered.

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1 INTRODUCTION

To optimise outcomes of student learning and to develop valuable skills for future employment, engineering courses often complement lectures with laboratory classes [1]-[4]. A combination of theoretical learning with laboratory experiments is of particular importance at German universities of applied sciences that aim for practice-guided learning [5].

The goal of implementing laboratories is to meet various learning objectives (such as instrumentation, experimental approaches, data analysis, safety and teamwork). Sometimes these objectives are not clearly formulated at the early stages of laboratory development [6]. Over the years, the efficacy of laboratory modes and advantages of different laboratory modes for teaching in general and for teaching engineering students in particular was discussed broadly [4], [7]. However, many studies in this field did not use strong methodological approaches, and therefore, it is difficult to attribute results of these studies to the influence of laboratory modes alone [4]. The goal of this study was therefore to compare laboratory modes of a battery basics course while keeping constant as many influencing factors as possible.

The present research focused on two modes in the local domain. In-person *hands-on* laboratories allow students to directly interact with the subject at hand and check the equipment even though this interaction might be mediated through technology or a user interface. In an in-person *simulated* laboratory, on the other hand, all of the students' interactions are moderated through a user interface, including procedures by which they create their understanding of the experimental hardware. Properties of the investigated effect or sample are simulated by computer software. Commonly, students work in a classroom equipped with computers on which simulations are running. With increasing complexity in teaching practical engineering skills via laboratories, borders between these modes often become blurry. Therefore, the perceived laboratory condition is also of interest when comparing laboratory modes.

In 2005, Euan D. Lindsay published results on perceived laboratory learning. Experiments were conducted in three perceived modes. Firstly, hands-on experiments in the local domain. Secondly, simulated experiments in the local domain. And thirdly, remote experiments (physically present experiments in the next room). The user interface was the same as for remote and simulated experiments. Technically, students calibrated a piezoelectric accelerometer using a laser-Doppler and a spectrum analyser. It was attempted to make the remote and simulated laboratory conditions as similar as possible. For example, in one of the experiments, the simulation group heard recorded sound from a real experiment, while the remote group heard sound from the actual experiment. Both the remote and the simulation group conducted the experiment from the same room. While checking the lab reports, Lindsay observed that the laboratory mode (hands-on, remote or simulated) influenced learning outcomes. The distance between students and equipment made the remote and the simulation groups more reflective since the two groups did better at noticing and adapting to unexpected results than the hands-on group. The

learning outcomes from the remote group and the simulation group, which had almost identical experiences, were not equal either. The simulation group paid more attention to the theory behind the experiment, and less attention to hardware and how it influenced the experiment. Lindsay noticed that the focus of students changed, because they knew that they were not using real hardware. He concluded that the students' attitude towards the laboratory was the deciding factor that affected the learning outcomes. [8]

While simulated experiments have become popular for conducting laboratory exercises in tertiary education due to obvious reasons (among others, repeatability and cost efficiency) [7], this study focuses on differences in learning outcomes of students by comparing hands-on and simulated laboratories. Moreover, simulations, which were framed as hands-on experiments, were used. This so-called *hidden simulation* condition was the final step in equalizing hands-on and simulated laboratories. It was added to determine whether or not there are any significant differences between these two modes if laboratory conditions itself are indistinguishable.

2 METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted in two consecutive phases. Study runs of both phases were carried out in local access domain. The objective of the first phase was to compare student learning through hands-on laboratories with that from simulated laboratories. Phase two was conceptualised to verify the quality of simulations used in phase one and at the same time give insight into possible subjective influences of the laboratory mode itself by comparing results of hands-on laboratories with laboratories in which hidden simulations were conducted.

As this study focused solely on comparing different learning modes, all other aspects such as accompanying lectures, experimental instructions, teachers, learning objectives, tests, working teams, and many more were held constant for compared conditions [9]. If improvements were possible in one of the modes (e.g. time-lapse in simulations), lessons were not optimised. Thus, this study does not determine which of the investigated laboratory modes has the potential to be the best to teach battery behaviours, but whether or not there are significant differences between hands-on and simulated laboratories when the same experiment is conducted. Also, a remote laboratory condition was not included in the comparison as this study solely compared in-person laboratory teaching with/without proper laboratory equipment in the local domain. Methodologies of both study phases are described in more detail below.

2.1 Laboratories, experiments, and instructions

Laboratories were part of different courses on battery basics designed for engineering students. Laboratory experiments on energy storages/lithium-ion batteries [10] were developed for all laboratory modes. Experimental procedures

were created so that each step (e.g. discharging the battery to reach a specific state of charge) was the same in all modes. Thus, it was possible to use the same set of written instructions for all modes. The instructions included preliminary questions, guidelines for the experiments, and advice on analysis and collection of data.

Each session was executed as follows. After meeting in the laboratory (hands-on/hidden simulations) or at the computer pool (simulations), the experiment was introduced. Students connected the prepared cell to the device and opened the graphical user interface (hands-on) or started the simulation, using the same GUI (simulated) [9].

Parameters of battery cells during simulations and hands-on experiments were displayed on the computer screen as graphs and values. Hidden simulations laboratories were equipped with modified devices that additionally displayed the momentary/simulated values of current and voltage.

All student teams worked autonomously in a supervised environment, following written instructions. To start an experiment, students defined current and voltage sequences for each measurement. All laboratory experiments consisted of a series of measurements to collect data (current, voltage, and temperature over time) which were evaluated before the next measurement or at home to produce the requested conclusions and graphs (e.g. internal resistance over the state of charge).

All learning objectives could be met by following the experimental procedure/instructions without any further help from the instructor. The same teacher supervised all laboratories. Since the study at hand focused on a strict methodological approach, a remote laboratory condition could not be included, even though many students favour online education [4], [7]. Also, it was found that it might be difficult for students to differentiate clearly between remote and simulated labs [11].

2.2 Methodology to compare laboratory conditions

In order to minimise the influence of various disturbing factors, an in-subject counterbalanced methodology similar to a crossover trial was implemented [12]: Participants were divided into two groups. Both groups had the same learning objectives, which were clustered around either two or four content areas depending on the study run, as shown in *Table 1*. Each group was divided into teams of three to five students who conducted all laboratory experiments together. [9]

Each group worked on content areas in the same order but switched laboratory condition between sessions. The first group conducted even experiments in experimental condition A while the second group conducted the same experiments in experimental condition B. For odd experiments, groups switched the respective conditions.

To assess the influence of laboratory modes on knowledge acquisition, a 10-minute test was held approximately two weeks after each laboratory session. The study was fully anonymous, and participants did not receive incentives for taking part.

TABLE 1: STUDY RUNS

Study Run	Students	Female	Background	CA	Semester of Studies
RA1 Electric Mobility (B. Eng.) 2016	40	5%	German	4	4
RA2 Electric Mobility (B. Eng.) 2017	30	13%	German	4	4
RA3 International Summer School 2017	32	12%	International	2	3-9
RB1 Electric Mobility (B. Eng.) 2018	29	10%	German	4	4
RB2 International Summer School 2018	39	9%	International	2	3-9
RB3 Renew. Energy Syst. (M. Sc.) 2018	45	13%	International	2	8
All Study Runs	215	<11%			

RA1-RA3: hands-on vs. simulations RB1-RB3: hands-on vs. hidden simulations

CA 2: (B*) open-circuit voltage, and (C*) internal resistance and power, 2:00 h each.

CA 4: (A) contact and isolation resistance, (B), (C), and (D) energy of cells, 2:50 h each.

2.3 First Phase: Hands-on vs. Simulation

As shown in *Table 1*, the first phase was carried out between 2016 and 2017 in three study runs (RA1 to RA3). 2nd year electric mobility bachelor students were instructed in German (RA1, RA2), participants of the other run because of a variety of backgrounds in English (RB3). The educational research was explained to the participants during the first session in detail. Due to meeting in differing rooms (laboratory vs. computer pool) and due to the absence/presence of measurement devices and batteries, students were always aware of the experimental condition.

Fig. 1. Hands-on devices (a) as well as simulation models (b) were controlled by the same graphical user interface.

For the simulated experiments, a black-box simulation model that imitated hands-on battery behaviour was designed and calibrated (*Fig. 1*).

2.4 Second Phase: Hands-on vs. Hidden Simulation

Phase two followed the same concept. Here, influences of the perceived learning mode were investigated by comparing *hidden simulations* (framed hands-on) to real hands-on experiments. This experiment was performed in three study runs in 2018 (RB1-RB3), as shown in *Table 1*.

This time, participants used hands-on equipment in laboratory environment in both conditions. In the hands-on condition, real measurements were shown. In the hidden simulations condition, results of simulated battery behaviour were displayed. Participants of hidden simulations were presented with data calculated by the same simulation model as in the first study phase. To flawlessly imitate the hands-on

condition, the output was not only shown on the computer screen but additionally displayed on the measurement devices (ref. Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. (a) The hands-on device (with a real battery cell) or (b) with “hidden simulations” the simulation model was controlled by students, using the same graphical user interface. The results are displayed on the GUI and the test bench’s displays while a battery cell is actually connected to the equipment. In that way in case of b) the students are not aware that they use simulations.

Participants were again aware of the ongoing engineering education study hands-on vs. simulations. However, this time, students were not aware of differences in data sources during their technical experiments: All students were given the *impression* that they were part of a *hands-on control group* for the full semester and therefore thought they all worked in the hands-on condition.

Fig. 3. Laboratory environment during hands-on experiments in the first phase and during hidden simulation as well as hands-on experiments in the second phase.

A lot of effort was spent on arranging these laboratories. Simulations (model, parameters) stayed the same as in previous runs, but computer-software and device-firmware [10] were extended to show simulation results in real-time on the device displays. A battery was connected, but no actual current was applied. Even the open/close sounds of the attached safety box were triggered. For a visitor it would not have been possible to distinguish the hidden simulation setups from hands-on setups when entering the laboratory or to determine that a comparison of lab conditions was running (ref. Fig. 3).

3 RESULTS

In all runs, participants' test results indicated reasonable knowledge retention with mean test scores ranging from 36% to 67%. In order to account for different group sizes and to exclude a potential influence of differences in difficulties of the content areas, data transformation was used. The difference between a student's individual scored percentage and mean percentage of all participants in the same test (e.g. mean result of all students of RA1 in content area A) was calculated and divided by the standard deviation of the respective content area from that run. This method is called Studentization [13], and its result is considered the *student's performance* in a single test. A value above zero indicated that the student's performance was above average, a value below zero a below-average performance.

In order to determine which laboratory mode produced better learning outcomes, the averages of all students' test performances in the two experimental conditions hands-on and simulated were compared using an independent-sample t-test.

3.1 Results First Phase: Hands-on vs. Simulation

In total, 102 students participated in the first phase. In each individual study run students' test scores after hands-on exercises outperformed those after simulations (see Table 2).

Mean student performance after hands-on laboratories significantly exceeded mean student performance after simulation in the German runs (RA1-RA2, $t(261) = 2.40$, $p = .018$, Cohen's $d = .29$). In RA3, which was an international summer school, even though no significant effect was found, the mean and effect size point towards the same direction as do the German runs.

Overall results showed statistically significant differences in the learning outcomes favouring the hands-on condition (RA1-RA3, $t(317) = 2.45$, $p = .015$, Cohen's $d = .27$).

TABLE 2: FIRST PHASE: STUDENT'S TEST PERFORMANCE: COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

Study run	Hands-on			Simulated			df	t	p	d
	Tests	M	SD	Tests	M	SD				
RA1 B. Eng.	73	.12	.96	75	-.11	1.01	146	1.42	.158	.23
RA2 B. Eng.	58	.18	.83	57	-.18	1.10	113	2.01 *	.048	.37
RA3 Summer	28	.09	.94	28	-.09	1.05	54	0.65	.521	.17
RA1,2 Ger.	131	.15	.90	132	-.14	1.05	261	2.40 *	.018	.29
All	159	.13	.91	160	-.13	1.05	317	2.45 *	.015	.27

* = $p < .05$ d = Cohen's d (pos. = adv. of hands-on)

Since all lab modes were created to be very similar, the reason for these differences was unclear. The influence of the perceived laboratory mode was assumed to be major influencing factor.

3.2 Results Second Phase: Hands-on vs. Hidden Simulation

In total, 113 students participated in the second phase. *Table 3* shows the comparison of student’s performances after real hands-on experiments with performances after hidden simulations (presented as hands-on experiments). None of the study runs (individual or in sum) showed a significant difference. Results of RB1 even showed a trend towards advantages of hidden simulations.

TABLE 3: SECOND PHASE: STUDENT’S TEST PERFORMANCE: COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS

Study run	real hands-on			hidden simulations			df	t	p	d
	Tests	M	SD	Tests	M	SD				
RB1 B. Eng.	55	-.16	.98	56	.16	.98	109	-1.74 †	.085	-.33
RB2 Summer	19	.02	.92	19	-.02	1.08	36	.09	.930	.03
RB3 M. Sc.	33	-.02	1.00	33	.02	1.00	64	-.13	.896	-.03
RB2,3 int.	52	-.01	.96	52	.01	1.02	102	-.05	.959	-.01
All	107	-.09	.97	108	.09	1.00	213	-1.28	.203	-.17

† = $p < .10$ d = Cohen’s d (pos. = adv. of real hands-on)

4 DISCUSSION

Results of the first phase suggest that traditional hands-on experiments lead to better learning outcomes compared to simulations when teaching battery basics. This result was unexpected since hands-on experiments were conducted very similarly to simulated laboratories. The simulation model was devised by battery experts in order to imitate battery behaviour in the most realistic way. No perceived differences in battery behaviour were found in the students’ protocols. The obtained result is contrary to the recent surge of studies reporting better or equal learning with non-traditional (virtual/simulated) labs [4], [7].

Nevertheless, hidden weaknesses of the simulation model could not be excluded completely. These could have influenced students’ learning negatively. To validate the simulation model and assess the role of the perceived laboratory mode, the usage of simulations was framed as hands-on experiments and compared to results of hands-on laboratories in the second test phase. Here, no significant differences in learning outcomes of participants were found, suggesting that the simulations used worked as they should and the differences between the two conditions hands-on and simulated of phase one can be attributed to the perceived laboratory mode.

Lindsay’s study (2005) evaluating lab-protocols delivered insight in the student’s change of attitude depending on the laboratory mode the experiments were held in. The present research differs, as it focused on a specific subject (battery cells) where even in hands-on mode investigated physical dimensions were not tangible/audible (e.g. current and voltage) and where very little physical interaction with equipment was necessary. Smaller differences in learning outcomes between groups are to be expected when no interaction with the experimental setup is needed, compared to Lindsay’s accelerometer experiment or for example an experiment in which the

relation of the length of a pendulum and its period of oscillation is to be determined and thus, students frequently have to touch the investigated objects.

As hidden differences in the simulations could be excluded from having been the reason for inferior learning outcomes, psychological effects need to be considered to comprehend the effectiveness of the different laboratory modes. The students could have felt that simulated experiments were less relevant, and they might have lost some of the motivation to comprehend and remember what they had experienced and learned during the laboratory exercises. Also, the environments the laboratories took place in (scientific lab vs. computer pool) could have had an influence. This needs to be examined in future studies.

However, there are several study limitations that need to be addressed. Most of the analysed data is based on students from one German university of applied sciences enrolled in the same B. Eng. program “electric mobility” (RA1, RA2, and RB1). Due to the small number of participants in the international runs, overall results mainly reflect results from German B. Eng. students. Nevertheless, the international run with a mixed student background (RA3) showed better knowledge acquisition with hands-on laboratories as well. In addition, results are not generalizable to student populations with a higher share of female participants, as in all runs the majority of participants were male.

5 CONCLUSION

While Lindsay (2005) reviewed laboratory protocols and thereby determined the quality of the work and focus of the students in the respective conditions, findings of this study are based on written knowledge tests. Significant differences between the influence of simulation and hands-on laboratories in local domain on learning were discovered in the first phase of this study. Hands-on laboratories produced better test results. In the second phase of this study, the role of perception of the laboratory condition on student learning was examined. This time, learning environment and equipment used was the same in both conditions. Subjects involved in simulated laboratories thought that they conduct hands-on experiments. Under these circumstances, no significant differences were found in students' test results.

It is reasonable to assume that differences in test results between laboratory conditions in phase one would have been even higher, had the experimental procedure included physical interaction. However, this would have altered only the hands-on condition, and therefore it would have been impossible to directly compare results of hands-on and simulated laboratories.

It was found that the learning environments which seemed to be connected to real-world implications (action and reaction were perceived “hands-on”) produced better learning outcomes. Nevertheless, it needs to be pointed out, that the authors do not recommend to trick students into thinking they are using devices which they are actually not. For example, combining cost-saving simulations with cheap “fake

devices” (only a display). It is obviously unethical to do so outside of educational research.

6 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS AND OUTLOOK

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Results presented in this paper are part of an ongoing study. More data will be collected during summer semester 2019. Further studies will investigate the relationship between learning outcomes in the laboratory conditions hands-on, simulated, as well as hidden simulation and the educational experiences and background of the students (e.g. the completion of a vocational education and training program before studies, and practical experiences before enrolling in the study program).

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